

Literature review: beyond-CMOS technologies

Part of the UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project

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This section is a discussion of the very comprehensive (over a thousand references) report on the topic, the IEEE International Roadmap for Devices and Systems (IRDS) 2021 Edition¹, *Beyond CMOS* [5]. The report looked at many aspects of post-CMOS technologies but there is not mention at all of the key issues related to sustainability of future computing devices. Additional sources are referenced explicitly.

1 Post CMOS

CMOS scaling is projected to stop by 2027. For the market that probably means 2030. There is as yet no clear candidate to replace CMOS, but there are a large number of technologies that are similar enough to be mature by 2040. It typically takes about 20 years for a technology to become commercially mainstream given enough investment. For example, blue LEDs were introduced in 1993; SSD drives in 1991; GPUs in 1999 and FPGAs in the late 1980s. In practice, this means that any technology that currently is not at TRL4 will not be available before 2040. So a likely scenario is that performance per Watt will stagnate from 2030 for five to ten years. It will certainly not improve compared to the current trend before 2040.

Furthermore, a key observation from [3] is that the GHG emissions per cm² of wafer have increased linearly with every subsequent generation. Most of the emissions result from the energy required to operate the fab and the various production chemicals with very high GHG potential used in the manufacturing process. Processes for the first generations of post-CMOS technologies will be very similar because the aim of these technologies is to be drop-in replacement for CMOS so they can be manufactured in similar fabs. To compound this, the die sizes have also grown with every generation. As a result, embodied carbon in CPUs, GPUs and RAM show an ever-increasing trend.

In conclusion, the emissions from manufacturing of post-CMOS ICs are likely to be of the same order as today for at least 2040.

¹<https://irds.ieee.org/editions/2021>

2 Main observations on storage

As the carbon footprint of SDD is much higher than that of RAM, I have focused on the former.

- SSD will keep increasing in density until about 2040, and will keep using the current technologies.
- Denser SSD in particular does not mean lower embodied carbon: the higher density is obtained by stacking more vertical layers and every layer means an additional pass of the wafer through the fab, so the energy consumption of manufacturing increases with the density. Furthermore, increasing the density by moving to a smaller feature size increases the carbon footprint per wafer [3]. So in practice, higher-density SSDs will have an even higher carbon footprint per unit of storage.
- It is worth noting that for server applications, the total lifetime carbon footprint of magnetic disks is much lower than that of SSD [7]
- The focus of the industry is on increasing the density more than reducing the energy per bit, and embodied carbon is not even discussed.
- In the further future, DNA storage is likely to be viable, is extremely low power as well as having very low embodied carbon. However, this is highly unlikely to be mainstream by 2040.

In conclusion, at least until 2040, advances in data storage will not lead to a reduction emissions from data storage, and likely even lead to an increase per unit of data stored.

3 Main observations on beyond-CMOS computational technologies

The ITRS report discusses a number of viable beyond-CMOS technologies but most of these are likely to take the shape of specialised accelerators rather than mainstream CPUs. All of them are still in very early stages, but several of them are particularly promising in terms of energy consumption, in particular analog computing approaches and adiabatic computing which could lead to accelerators for matrix-vector multiplication, linear equation solvers and differential equations solvers.

Neuromorphic computing, esp. spiking neuron architectures, have been built and evaluated in the past 20 years, but (maybe somewhat surprisingly), they have not even shown to be viable alternatives to conventional digital synchronous silicon even for the closest match, i.e. deep learning. A key problem is the programming model, but they also need more efficient mechanisms for direct point to point communication. It is therefore unlikely that they will become dominant in future

Quantum computing is a special case in that it is not inherently low power but for some classes of algorithms can achieve exponential speed-ups, so that even with the

current technologies, for specific problems a quantum accelerator might be the most energy-efficient choice. The embodied carbon of such machines is as yet unknown. The main barrier to adoption is again the programming model. The experience with FPGAs and spiking-neuron machines has shown that development and adoption of alternative programming models is very slow, so even if quantum accelerators would be available commercially by 2030, it might easily take another 20 years before they are mainstream in scientific computing.

The ITRS report does not consider biological computing (DNA computing etc). Based on a few recent papers [2, 4, 6, 1], it is clear that this branch of computing is in the very early stages yet but that it has huge potential because of the small size and very low energy consumption.

In conclusion, none of the beyond-CMOS computational technologies can help us with getting to net zero by 2030. It will likely take until 2050 before some of them become mainstream, in particular because the most promising technologies in terms of sustainability (low embodied carbon, low energy consumption) will also require radically different programming models, which is likely to slow down adoption in similar fashion as seen by the advent of multicore and accelerator technologies.

References

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